

INTELLIGENCE, THE FOUNDATION OF MATTER

(by Albert Hoffmann – 2019)

[01] All the ideas presented in this article are based on the writings of Jakob Lorber who between 1840 until his death in 1864 wrote 25 volumes under divine inspiration. This monumental work is referred to as the New Revelation (NR) and the books can be read for free online at the Internet Archive at <https://archive.org/details/BeyondTheThreshold>. It contains the most extraordinary deepest of wisdom ever brought to paper and touches on every conceivable subject of life. Internationally renowned statistician, economist and philosopher E.F. Schumacher who became famous for his best-seller "Small is Beautiful", commented about the NR in his book "A Guide for the Perplexed" as follows: "*They (the books of the NR) contain many strange things which are unacceptable to modern mentality, but at the same time contain such plethora of high wisdom and insight that it would be difficult to find anything more impressive in the whole of world literature.*" (1977).

[02] In these writings accurate predictions were made concerning future events effecting mankind as a whole like weapons of mass destruction and the cold war, pollution of the atmosphere with hydrocarbons and its consequences, destruction of the rainforests and resulting catastrophic weather phenomena, the internet and many others. The writings completed in 1864 also reveal scientific facts many years before they were actually discovered by science. Examples of these are the existence of billions of galaxies in the universe while the first galaxies outside of the Milky Way were discovered by Hubble only in 1925. The NR accurately describes a structured universe consisting of galaxies, super galaxies and super-super galaxies which only most recently (after 1960) were observed and referred to as galaxy clusters and super clusters. But also with regard to the micro cosmos the NR foretold that atoms can be further broken down into sub-atomic particles which eventually reach the level of massless quantum particles having a life span of 10^{-18} seconds as only discovered by modern physics. In a like manner also the dual character of light (particle and wave behaviour) and that light moves as electro-magnetic waves has been stated ten years (1852) before Maxwell published his electro-magnetic wave equations in 1861 to 1862. All these accurately predicted scientific facts lends a strong credibility to the NR which should no longer be ignored by official science.

[03] There are however, also controversial issues which need to be looked at more closely like it is stated in the NR that our solar system orbits around the star Sirius in 28,000 years and that Sirius, the centre of a dwarf galaxy, is orbiting the centre of the Milky Way.

[04] It should be noted that the scientific facts as stated above are not documented well structured all in one place but are rather spread as bits and pieces all over the 25 volumes of the NR. It really requires to study all 25 volumes carefully to obtain a clear picture of what has been said and meant. I have done this on an on and off basis since 1977 for more than forty years with a heightened interest towards my later years. However, it is not really the scientific content which is so compelling but rather the overwhelming wisdom filled spiritual message touching on every aspect of life which forms the bulk of these writings and are so heart warming to read.

[05] The dominant church engineered superstitious mindset of mankind prevailing during mediaeval times, threatened to inhibit the further development of the human soul at large. To break this superstitious dogma holding the human mind captive for so long, mankind was allowed to develop natural science. Science certainly succeeded in freeing the human mind from superstition of which the internet is the best example. But at the same time did the free-willingness of man quickly used science to satisfy his greed for wealth and power, guiding science on a pure materialistic pathway. Any research not leading to make money or supporting military endeavours, was and still is regarded as inferior. But the time has now come to open the door for a post materialistic approach to science. This article in particular focusses on intelligence as the foundation of matter and the universe at large and how this compares to the findings of modern day official science. The principals of how the universe works, encompassing the physical as well as spiritual realm as outlined in the NR, can be understood by everyone and not only by a small elite as it is the case with mainstream science.

[06] To get the discussion started let's begin with one of the most basic philosophies of science which is the principle of causality (cause and effect), addressed in depth already by the Greek philosopher Aristotle more than 2000 years ago. An object on a flat surface can be moved in various ways by applying a horizontal vector force to it. The object can be put in motion for example by pushing it by hand or using a stick or any other suitable machine. All means to move the object requires the manipulation or conversion of energy. If

moved by hand, bioenergy (basically stored sunlight) is turned into kinetic energy while when using an electric motor, electric energy (most likely also sunlight) is converted to kinetic energy. This is a classical example of cause and effect whereas the means by which the object is moved is called the cause and the movement of the object is the resulting effect. But an important component is missing from this analyses because something has to trigger the energy manipulation process. Irrespective if the object is moved by hand or stick or machine, it requires the intervention of human intelligence. But I also could open the window and let a gust of wind blow into the room which in turn could move the object on the table. It is not disputed that the opening of the window requires intelligence but what about the wind? The earth is revolving around its own axis allowing the sun to heat the atmosphere resulting in atmospheric temperature differences causing air to expand and begin to flow. Was the rotation of the earth caused by some kind of intelligence? Is there intelligence in sunlight? This line of thinking quickly finds its way back to the origin of the universe which will be addressed later on.

[07] At this juncture of the discussion it must be stressed that intelligence is seen separately from the function of the human brain. The human brain is just a very sophisticated hard drive to store information and to relay information back and forth between an independent functioning conscious entity inside of us and the human body. The human brain does not have a 'central processing unit' to see and interpret its own thoughts (stored information). Just like the hard drive of a computer cannot process its stored information but requires a central processing unit to do so. To support this very controversial notion, the reader is referred to the research of cardiologist Pim Van Lommel who for more than twenty years studied near-death experiences (NDEs) in patients who survived a cardiac arrest. In 2001, he and his fellow researchers published a study on Near Death Experiences in the renowned medical journal The Lancet. Their core findings were that after the brain ceased to function, patients were having the most unusual, joyful, positive real life experiences which permanently changed their personality afterwards. With this in mind, let's continue with our discussion of intelligence.

[08] Intelligence on its own is not able to move the object. Intelligence also requires a free will to act. My free willingness is prompting my intelligence to stretch out my arm and hand to apply my bioenergy to get the object moving. In summary it can be said it requires three components to cause an effect: intelligence, free willingness and power (energy or force). My free willingness could also be prompting my intelligence to apply my energy and power to find and prepare the necessary materials to build a machine to move the object. In this way all technological inventions of mankind are based on intelligence, free will and power. With physics and quantum mechanics, mainstream science has only addressed the notion of matter and power (energy) but completely ignored the equally crucial and inseparable notion of intelligence and free willingness. Hence it can be stated that wherever there is energy there is also intelligence and free willingness. Energy cannot be separated from intelligence and free willingness and therefore must always be viewed as an inseparable trinity. The law of conservation of energy equally applies to intelligence. It must be added that the availability of intelligence is infinitive just like energy is limitless. This means that all intelligence of past, present and future already exists, just like energy but can express itself in different forms. And just like energy occurs in tiny little measurable quantum packages, so does intelligence occurs equally in tiny small units of most basic pieces of intelligence. If these tiniest particles of intelligence are combining they constitute intelligence clusters, collectively forming higher level intelligence entities with reference to the separated individual intelligent units. More about this later on.

[09] Every word ever uttered, every action ever performed, every behaviour ever expressed, yes, even every thought ever created, irrespective how subtle, has intelligence as its foundation. If intelligence and free willingness are the most important aspects of our lives, why is it then that intelligence has been excluded from all particle science and quantum physics for so long? Just because intelligence is not detectable with our most sophisticated measuring devices and cannot physically be quantified, it doesn't mean to just sweep it under the rug and forget about it. Intelligence forms an integral component of all particles and matter. Mathematics, understood by only a very small elite, is not the final judge of what is true and what is not true. Neither will the answer be found in building bigger and more expensive tail chasing particle colliders, only for scientist to realize that they have discovered their very own intelligence. Especially now where science with quantum physics has reached a brick wall and has to rely more and more on "theoretical physics" which in turn uses all kinds of mathematical acrobatics to further mystify our understanding of the universe, it is high time to break completely new ground and view the origin and behaviour of matter from an entirely different perspective.

[10] To understand the universe in its entirety a holistic approach is required which includes the physical and the spiritual realm and where the quantum world can be regarded as a transitional realm (Fig. 1). The very intelligence which is used by scientists to seek the origin of matter must become an integral part of the

solution. The term 'spiritual' in this case does not carry a religious connotation but rather refers to a dimensional state of things outside of space and time with consciousness, intelligence and free willingness at its core. Take note that the spiritual realm is the true reality of the universe while the physical realm is only a temporary illusion necessary for the development of free-willing intelligence. This must be so because the spiritual realm existed long before matter came into being and will exist forever long after the last physical particle has dissolved in space. Our own short material life is the living proof for this. For quite some time after the Michelson/Morley experiment (1887) and relativity (1905), the ether became a taboo subject because relativity cannot exist with a moving ether. But a conflicted Einstein has been misunderstood in this regard because he himself had this to say about the ether: *"Recapitulating, we may say that according to the general theory of relativity space is endowed with physical qualities; in this sense, therefore, there exists an ether. According to the general theory of relativity space without ether is unthinkable; for in such space there not only would be no propagation of light, but also no possibility of existence for standards of space and time (measuring-rods and clocks), nor therefore any space-time intervals in the physical sense. But this ether may not be thought of as endowed with the quality characteristic of ponderable media, as consisting of parts which may be tracked through time. The idea of motion may not be applied to it."* (5 May 1920). Clearly Einstein was conflicted for on the one hand endowing the ether with physical properties and on the other hand denying it any characteristics of ponderable media. Therefore it is heartening to notice that in present day theoretical physics, the ether is brought back to life, even if only in terms of a field or multiple fields or for that matter 'strings'. For this line of thinking lends itself as a springboard for the so long overdue quantum leap to add intelligence and consciousness to the ether.

Fig. 1: Holistic view of the universe including both the physical and spiritual realm with the quantum world as the transitional realm.

[11] The quantum state of things is the transitional state between the physical realm and the spiritual realm. This is the reason why the physical laws applying to the physical macro cosmos do not equally well apply to the quantum world any longer. The physical laws governing matter do not apply to the spiritual dimension at all. In the spiritual world everything is based on intelligence and free will while these two properties are altogether absent in the physical world and this is the very reason why the physical world has to be governed by physical 'must' laws. All physical forms are just the corresponding, temporary expression of the inner spiritual content.

[12] In quantum physics for example it is stated that the two states of an electron (up spin and down spin) can exist in one place at the same time. In spiritual terms this can be explained as follows: Any space can be divided into smaller and smaller pieces indefinitely. Just like space also time can be divided into shorter and shorter time periods indefinitely. This is even more so the case in the spiritual dimension. Let's look at the following example: Imagine that mankind has succeeded in sending a man to Mars and returning him safely to earth. Back on earth again he will be able to tell us of his experience on Mars. In his mind this person will be able to imagine himself being on Mars in an instant and in the next moment be on earth again. So he/she can jump back and forth between earth and Mars instantly. Now, in the spiritual realm this jumping back and

forth can be increased to such a speed that it appears to an observer that he/she is at both places at the same time. This means an observer on earth will not be able to notice that the person has been absent at all and another observer on Mars will also see the astronaut continuously at the same time. If this is the case then space and time becomes obsolete in the spiritual dimension. In fact, a fully mature spirit can be anywhere in the universe at the same time if he/she chooses to do so.

[13] Up to now we only spoke about human intelligence. But what about animal and plant intelligence? It is easy to recognize the intelligence in large animals like elephants, dogs, dolphins, birds, apes, etc. But also a tiny shrimp can swim freely in any direction it wants, select the food it likes and engages in the reproduction process. If this intelligence is carefully analysed we find a lot of so called instinctive intelligence with a small measure of free willingness. Even viruses and bacteria are instinctively attracted to suitable food and reproduce and have all kinds of unique intelligence properties. When considering how plants respond to their environment with regard to light, temperature, moisture, air and minerals and how they know how, when and where to grow roots, stems, leaves, flowers and fruit, have the knowledge to produce their own unique molecules and construct an intricate network of valves and tubes, utilizing the process of osmosis and photosynthesis and finally store all this intelligence in a seed to pass it on to the next plant and having the ability to multiply infinitely, it is clear that this goes far beyond chemical reactions. Plant one thousand different seeds into the same soil and provide them with the same moisture, air and sunlight and one thousand different plant species will start to grow. Some kind of spiritual intelligence must be present to activate, regulate and harmonize all these processes. Leading researchers in the field of plant intelligence are Jack Schulz (Missouri), Oliver Hamant (Lyon) and Daniel Chamovitz (Tel Aviv). Jack Schulz sums it up best when stating "*Plants are just very slow animals.*"

[14] Having covered the intelligence of humans, animals and plants, let's see if we can look for intelligence in minerals. Dr Masaru Emoto took photos from ice crystals formed by the same water sample but exposing the water to different conditions. Water which was treated with love produced more beautiful crystals than the same water treated badly (e.g. cursing). Figure 2 shows the difference of water crystals taken from the Fujiwara Dam. After blessing the water through prayer and meditation for an hour, the crystals came out much more beautiful than before. The core findings of his research show the intelligent behaviour of water exposed to different conditions. Dr Masaru Emoto has been widely criticized for his findings and the way he conducted his research. However, a combined research project undertaken by Dr Emoto and Dr Dean Radin from the Institute of Noetic Sciences, in Petaluma, California, US consisting of a triple blind study where the intentioners, the raters and the photographers were kept independent of each other, confirmed the results by Dr Emoto.

[15] Another example of mineral intelligence can be found in the field of homeopathic solutions. Jerman, Berden and Škarja (1998) conducted a research project to examine the memory properties of water by means of Kirlian electro-photography. They were able to show that the effect of a substance dissolved in water was steadily increasing with an increase of levels of dilution. The effects of the substance continued to show (grow in intensity) even when the solution was diluted to such an extent that no molecules of the original substance were present in the solution any longer. The reader is also referred to the work done by Professor Konstantin Korotchov (1998) showing the memory effects of a drop of water impregnated by an intensive conscious mind exercise (Fig. 3). Korotchov also found that the information impregnated in water could be transferred to other samples of water or even to living organisms.

[16] If it can be shown that a mineral like water has intelligence there is no reason not to believe that all other minerals also have some kind of intelligence. To illustrate this further consider the findings of two Soviet physicists Dmitrii Blokhintsev and Fedor Galperin who in 1934 for the first time postulated the existence of a hypothetical sub-elementary particle called '*graviton*'. It is said that the *graviton*, a massless subatomic particle, if discovered, moves with the speed of light and facilitates gravity (according to science). Going one step further one can conclude that this massless, subatomic particle facilitating gravity, is in fact the very reason for gravity and is therefore gravity itself. If an object does not contain *gravitons*, it in fact does not have gravity. The metal aluminium has many fewer *gravitons* than for instance the same size piece of iron and still, the *graviton* itself is a massless particle but only contains the intelligence and power to move mass. Thus pulling or pushing an object in the direction of affinity. The ability to sense the direction of affinity is not subject to space and time and therefore is not dependent on a so called field. The *graviton* intelligence has thus the power to pull/push the object towards the centre of the earth despite being massless. Its free willingness in this case is expressed by love (affinity) to return to its origin, namely the centre of the earth or any other celestial body from where it originated.

[17] Similar to the *graviton* intelligence unit, the ether is filled with a countless variety of intelligence particles. In the original German publication of the NR the term "Spezifikum" is used to describe massless, single intelligence particles. In this article the Italian translation is used for "Spezifikum" namely "*specifica*". Thus a *specifica* refers to the smallest, massless and most basic single intelligence unit. *Specifica* are imponderable, indestructible intelligence units containing a unique intelligence property, a small proportionate degree of free willingness and power or energy, collectively forming living entities of consciousness. Of greatest relevance is the fact that *specifica* can exist freely without a material shell while any material shell can not exist without *specifica*. Infinite space is filled with an almost infinite variety of different *specifica* and so are the quantities of each, collectively called the ether. There doesn't exist one tiniest little speck of space without *specifica*. Even the 'empty space' inside the atom is filled with *specifica*. Some of the *specifica* in infinite space are bound in the endless number of shapes of matter while others exists freely in the spiritual realm. *Specifica* are destined to combine into *specifica* clusters to form ever higher levels of intelligent life or be absorbed by already higher levels of intelligence clusters. Matter serves as a suitable medium to ripen/consolidate *specifica* clusters. Once matter has served its purpose it dissolves into low level leftover *specifica* used for new clusters to develop. The existence of *specifica* makes the universe a living entity where everything is interconnected. A vague resemblance of this phenomena in official science could perhaps be found in quantum entanglement. The highest form and final destiny of *specifica* is the human soul. For a free willing intelligent human soul, consisting of countless many *specifica*, passing the school of all material forms to develop and reach maturity takes many many trillion years to accomplish. The emphasis here is on the development of free willingness.

[18] In very much the same way as Blokhintsev and Galperin calculated the hypothetical existence of the *graviton*, it should be possible to identify other similar intelligence *specifica*. For example we notice the differing hardness for various materials. Sticking to the Latin nomenclature we might call it the '*duriton*'. This *specifica* holds the intelligence of complete selfishness. Another property found in materials is flexibility (perhaps called '*flexiton*' or '*lentiton*') which can be described as humble compliance and is of a more superior nature than *graviton* and *duriton*. Through the *specifica* of dissolubility (perhaps called '*reneriton*' or '*liberiton*'), materials can be dissolved in fire or acid. This *specifica* harbours the intelligence of freedom which, under the right conditions, entrains all other *specifica*. It is also the *specifica* responsible for the centrifugal force and would keep on expanding to infinity if not contained by another *specifica* which expresses itself as unshakable perseverance. This latter *specifica* (perhaps called '*centriton*') wants to withdraw in itself, thus controlling the previous 'freedom' *specifica* as a centripetal force and vice versa. The glowing of iron in fire is the result of a rage *specifica* which normally rests. Only when agitated does it threaten to consume all other *specifica*. All the *specifica* described so far are of a telluric nature. An example of sidereal *specifica* from the stars is unification. The unification principal carries active love at its foundation and permeates and surrounds a mineral. The great eagerness of certain metals to absorb electricity can be attributed to the intelligence of movement and with it the thirst for social unification. Both, the unification and electricity absorption *specifica*, are not bound in minerals like the telluric *specifica* but permeates and surrounds it. The physical effect of the electricity absorption *specifica* in metals is rust. Along similar lines it is quite easy to spiritually identify a great number of core *specifica* in elementary minerals, mineral composites and plants. Many *specifica* have already been identified by science in quantum field theory but perhaps not valued in the right context. The intelligence of *specifica* clusters always express itself collectively and not individually with some *specifica* featuring more prominent than others subject to external environmental factors. Expanding this thought leads to the conclusion that there exist many more basic elements in the universe than the 120 elements in our periodic table. Single element minerals consist of about eight to twenty

specifica. In plants this number increases to thousands and in animals to millions and billions while a human soul is made up of countless many *specifica*.

[19] To further illustrate that intelligence can influence matter over distance, let's look at another research project conducted by Dr Dean Radin. Many of you are familiar with the double slit experiment in which particles are fired through a double slit causing an interference pattern on a projector screen which is the typical result of wave action. However, it can be argued (perhaps also expected) that particles passing through a double slit should produce only a two stripe pattern on the screen corresponding with the two slits (Fig. 4). To investigate this more closely a device has been added to the experiment to observe each particle individually as it is coming out of one of the two slits. The mystery arises from the following results obtained: If the observation device is switched off a normal wave like interference pattern is visible. However, the moment the observation device is switched on the interference pattern collapses and changes into a particle behaviour two stripe pattern. How is it possible for the particles to know when they are observed or not? In search for an answer to this question various theories have been postulated with no conclusive explanation to this day. But the result also led scientist to the conclusion of the dual character of light expressing wave

and particle behaviour at the same time. What Radin tried to do, is to investigate the possibility if the outcome of the double slit experiment (interference pattern vs two stripe pattern), could also be obtained through a mind exercises by asking participants to visualize seeing the particles exiting the two slits. Radin's experiment was set up in such a way that participants from thousands of miles away could take part over the internet, showing that distance does not play a role in the outcome. His research conducted over a period of three years in fact confirmed that intelligence was able to effect the outcome of the double slit experiment.

[20] The topic of mind over matter cannot be concluded without the mentioning of spiritual healings. It is very unfortunate that spiritual healing became a tainted subject through many fake, publicity stunt church healings. Nevertheless, there have also been many scientifically observed spiritual healing cases documented, like the study done by Dr Hodges and Dr Scofield which has been published in the Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine in April of 1995. The following is a citation from the report "*Clearly, a body of sound research has now been accumulated which for many supports the reality of healing beyond reasonable doubt and provides evidence that healing can occur when psychological factors, which may manifest as the placebo response, have been eliminated or allowed for in the analysis.*" Both, contact and distance healings have been investigated. Spiritual healing is thus another scientifically proven phenomena of manipulating matter through consciousness.

[21] The human genome consists of 22 chromosomes divided into 3 billion base pairs with 155 million variations. This is just the blueprint to set up our bodies and does not determine our free willing intelligence. First of all it requires an incredible amount of intelligence to set up this complex DNA pattern to begin with and it requires even more executable intelligence to physically construct a human body according to the DNA pattern. Designing a skyscraper on paper will not get it build. Thousands of workers and tons of materials will have to be coordinated intelligently to get the job done. Is there anybody who wants to suggest that over a

few million years 'dead' particles will be able to build skyscrapers by themselves through a process called evolution? With all the combined knowledge of all scientists in the world including all of the most modern laboratory facilities imaginable, man is not able and will never be able to produce even a small ant from particles alone and without the use of an already living cell. Man has an excellent track record to interfere with nature and mess things up because we think we understand nature but the sad truth is we don't. It is pretty amazing that almost on a molecular cell level, living organisms understand, interpret and execute the DNA blueprint in consideration with external environmental factors. This process is just unthinkable to take place without any form of intelligence.

[22] The body of any living organism consists of countless many physical particles which in turn are made up of *specifica*. But besides the *specifica* of the body the living organism also contains a separate higher level intelligence soul cluster. This soul cluster is added to the seed of an organism just before germination/inception and has the necessary intelligence to construct/grow its own body, constantly extracting and absorbing the most refined and highest level intelligence *specifica* from the nourishment adsorbed throughout its physical lifetime. This includes *specifica* from the earth, atmosphere, sun, stars (light and cosmic rays) and our interactions with each other and the environment. During this process the living organism is assisted in its growth period by higher level nature spirits overseeing the orderly development of all species. After reaching maturity inside its physical body, the ripened soul cluster loses interest in its physical jacket which is indicated by the ailing of the body and eventually separates from it. As a free roaming soul entity in the spiritual realm it is attracted by 'like minded' soul entities to combine with them to form a new higher level soul cluster which in turn is then again placed inside a seed for the next growth/consolidation cycle. In this way the intelligence clusters are developing to ever higher levels of intelligence (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: The development path of intelligence clusters through the mineral-, plant- and animal kingdom to form a fully intelligent human soul.

[23] Let's assume for a moment that the element hydrogen consists of eight *specifica* and the element oxygen carries ten *specifica*. If hydrogen and oxygen combine to form water, it is not that simple to add the number of *specifica* together and expect the total number of *specifica* to be eighteen. First it must be considered that some of the *specifica* occurring in hydrogen are also present in oxygen, thus in fact reducing the total sum of *specifica*. Secondly, during the process of binding, other new *specifica* are incorporated from the surrounding ether to form the mineral water which might end up having twenty *specifica* or more. When carefully analysing the physical-, chemical- and electrical properties of the elements in the periodic table in a kind of spiritual sense, it should not be too difficult to identify the basic *specifica* of all material particles which

should not exceed a total number of two-thousand. But one level up where many elements form oxides the sum can quickly reach perhaps ten-thousand for all different types of oxides. It goes to show the rather insignificant small number of *specifica* bound in elementary matter when compared to an almost infinite pool of *specifica* filling endless space and eventually finding its way into a human soul.

[24] The process of formation of matter as presented in Figure 6, has already been documented in the NR during the mid eighteen-hundreds when the existence of sub-atomic particles was not yet known to scientists. The first sub-atomic particle, the electron, was only discovered by J.J. Thomson in 1897 while the first pair production in a photon-photon collision was calculated by Lev Landau in 1934 and subsequently observed in Patrick Blackett's counter-controlled cloud chamber. As stated earlier, the ether is made up of an infinite variety and quantity of *specifica* also referred to as ether electrons. The ether electron is a massless particle with no resistance but has a charge. Ether electrons have the inclination towards total inactivity. But this never happens because the ether everywhere is always penetrated by light photons, a close relative to the ether electron. Photons constantly keep the ether electrons agitated to a greater or lesser degree. This agitation progressively increases inside galaxy space, solar systems and near suns and planets. In inter-stellar space the interaction between photons and ether electrons form the first class of animal life called "animalcules". The lifespan of these animalcules is 10^{-18} seconds. Inside solar systems, with an stepped-up light action, a second class of animal life is formed called "monads" with a life-span of 10^{-15} seconds. In the outer vicinity of the sun, planets, moons and comets, aided by the high-speed movement of celestial bodies through space, the lifespan of particles increases in steps of 10^{-3} until a lifespan of 10^{-9} seconds is reached. During this process the particles use light photons as food and retain more or less the same size, round shape. Particles, or for that matter animals, which live for 10^{-9} seconds and longer, start to leave

Fig. 6: The formation of matter to host the development of spiritual content.

behind a surviving shell which then form the first permanent sub-atomic particles. These sub-atomic particles combine in the region of the higher atmosphere to form atoms, sometimes even micro meteorites, which eventually will reach the surface of the earth. In this way, the earth, itself a living organism, receives its nourishment from the ether.

[25] The process described above, not all together unfamiliar to science, leads to the formation of particles or matter as such with a comparable low level of intelligence. But what is far more significant is the parallel formation of new higher level intelligent life potencies during this process and whereby matter is actually only a leftover by-product. Note that even during the very inception of matter, particles are already referred to as 'animals' like animalcules and monads, thus living organisms. Visible matter, irrespective how insignificant small or large, is always the carrier of an inner, dynamically evolving intelligence cluster.

[26] The formation of particles out of a living ether holds far reaching consequences for science. Perhaps the most significant effect it has is on the behaviour of light. The formation of animalcules and monads in interstellar space and solar system space respectively must inevitably lead to a density difference in relation to inter-galactic space. Light passing from inter-galactic space through interstellar and solar system space might start to bend because of the density difference. This could explain the phenomena of gravitational lensing. Without treading on the lion's tail, the increase of ether density, especially in the vicinity of the sun would also provide a simple explanation for the bending of light in the 1919 eclipse experiment by Eddington. The tail of a comet near the sun is conveniently explain with a phenomena called solar wind but could equally be explained by an increase of ether density near the sun starting to generate friction with the gravitational acceleration of the comet and subsequent heating. Without any 'frictional' ether present, only a uniformly spherical cloud of dust surrounding the comet would be visible. Hopefully sufficient sensitive equipment has been added to the current operating Parker probe orbiting the sun to shed more light on this topic.

[27] Even from the most hardened scientific perspective it is unthinkable that human intelligence and life or consciousness as such can develop from completely 'dead', unconscious particles. What is even more unimaginable, is to think that a supposed singularity could have existed in a complete empty infinite space devoid of anything. If particles are behaving according to certain physical or chemical laws, it must be assumed that the intelligence of physical laws must have predated the formation of the particles because the particles are forming according to certain already existing physical principles. The same can be said about the questionable singularity and big bang. All the intelligence of the universe, past present and future, must have existed before the putative singularity came into being since the formation and explosion of the singularity was already governed by certain physical laws. Or did the 'dead', unconscious particles originating from the singularity (based on non-existing physical laws?) started to develop intelligence after the explosion to develop the incredible well organized galaxies and all associated phenomena of the universe? If this is the case the intelligence could only have come from the surrounding ether which, again, must have been present before the big bang. Hence, the singularity and the big bang never could have existed. Alternatively it therefore makes perfect sense to state that matter in its endless diversity formed from an even by far more diverse pool of existing intelligence of which our own invisible intelligence is the most potent proof. And the first person who has documented this phenomena was the Apostle John when under divine inspiration wrote: "*1. In the beginning was the Word (intelligence), and the Word was with God, and the Word was God.*" "Beginning" is just a poor translation and is not the term used by John since it implies a time related beginning which is not true. A better translation for "Beginning" would be "In primordial essence..." or "From time immemorial..." or "In the primal cause...". The "Word" (intelligence) existed forever and has no beginning. It is now easy to visualize that this vast, infinite pool of intelligence, which has no beginning and no end, must have a universal, unlimited, centralized, perfect consciousness in the form of a man. And only this omnipotent, omniscient perfect being in its infinite wisdom, could have generated the ultimate thought, namely to reproduce itself. And this centralized most perfect consciousness we call God of whom, each and every person ever lived and to be living, carries a perfect image inside of himself. It is quite difficult for our time and space impaired soul thinking ability to understand the concept of a spiritual realm with no beginning and no end because our souls have been created and therefore have a beginning. But we are also endowed with a higher spiritual thinking ability (if developed) for which it is very natural to comprehend a timeless infinity dimension.

[28] Above it was the aim of this discussion to build a case for intelligence being the most basic building blocks of the universe and not material particles as believed by mainstream science. Material particles and ensuing physical shapes are just an outer downstream expression of the inner intelligent consciousness of everything in existence. This also applies to man himself. For if man does not understand himself, how can he understand his environment? As presented in Figure 7 every human being consists of a physical body, a

substantive soul and a divine spirit. Just like the physical body consisting of trillions of particles, in very much the same way is the soul made up of countless many intelligence particles (*specifica*). The soul can thus be defined as a substantive, intangible, intelligent, indestructible entity consisting of countless intelligence particles functioning collectively as a human being. Once the individual intelligence clusters (nature spirits) have merged to form a human soul, it cannot be broken up again. This is a rather important statement since disfigured remnants of this teaching can be found in some eastern religions where it is believed that people can be reincarnated into animal bodies, leading to all kinds of superstitious beliefs. This, however, cannot take place and would be against God's order.

[29] Bear in mind that the soul, before born into a human body, has completed a many trillion year long journey as separated intelligence clusters, progressively unifying and consolidating in and out of matter to ever higher levels of intelligence. It goes without saying that all experiences and knowledge gained from the very first inception of the first *specifica* of the soul's being, remains an integral part of the soul and is forever preserved. Being incarnated into a human body is the soul's final and last leg in matter. Once having completed the earthly life, the soul will not return to matter again and will continue its development in the spiritual world only. In rare cases, however, when a soul has damaged itself through a life of selfishness and haughtiness to such an extent that a pure spiritual progress is not possible, it might be allowed to be reincarnated under severe challenging circumstances to learn humility. In extreme cases this process of rehabilitation can lead to even more than one reincarnation. The overall purpose here is for the soul to rid itself of self-love and the love for matter. Since all matter exists in a state of judgement subject to physical "must" laws which impairs the freedom of the soul, it is the destiny of the soul to free itself from matter and not to embrace matter, in order to become fully free.

Fig. 7: The spiritual anatomy of man consisting of a physical body, a substantive soul and a divine spirit.

[30] The not yet perfected soul, though a spiritual entity, does not have the capacity to see the physical world. It uses the five senses of the body to understand the material world. The brain stores all the information gathered by the five senses and the soul has the ability to understand and process these pictures and thoughts stored in the brain. It is reiterated that the physical brain, being itself a product of substantive intelligence particles, does not have the ability to see and interpret its own pictures, thus the physical brain cannot think. All thinking, feeling, comprehension, conclusions, reasoning, perceptions, assessing concepts on a higher level, etc. takes place in the mind which is located inside the soul. Hence, the free willingness of man is also located inside the soul. The soul, through the brain and nerve system, relays information to the various body parts. The soul is ultimately responsible how it has used its body during its entire physical life. Bear in mind that the body has its own autonomous natural life as to heartbeat and functioning of the organs of which the soul knows very little about. However, without the soul and spirit the body immediately ceases to function which is known as the death of a person.

[31] When departed from the physical realm the soul will become the creator of its own environment and will keep on doing what it loved most doing on earth. If a person passionately loved gardening, he/she will create its own garden landscape and grow plants as before, similar to a very vivid animated dream. The over-enthusiastic astronomer will roam from one solar system to the next to marvel at God's creation until such time when also he/she will realize that there is a lot more to life than stargazing. This means the soul now has to rely on its very own deepest beliefs, passions, truths, perceptions, loves, knowledge, experiences, behaviour, etc. which it has collected during its physical life on earth. When the soul has submerged itself too deep in matter during its earthly life, it will only experience its own fantasies of darkness and limbo of matter and despite the resulting suffering it will be virtually impossible to change her mind because its engrained beliefs becomes the very reality world she wants to live in not able to see it differently. Even God cannot interfere with the free-willingness of the soul without turning it into a puppet and thereby destroying its very purpose of life to become a free-willing God resembling person. Only the greatest unimaginable loving patience of the Creator can find ways to guide such a soul back to salvation. However, if a soul succeeded in its earthly life to find the Creator in itself and actively cares for the well-being of its fellow-men, the Creator Himself becomes her inner reality which can only be described as "No eye has seen, no ear has heard, and no mind has imagined what God has prepared for those who love him." (1 Corinthians 2:9).

[32] The outer shape of the soul is very much the same as the physical body. In a higher spiritual corresponding manner the soul consists of the same organs as the body. However, since the soul comprises of only the most refined intelligence particles, its appearance is by far more beautiful compared to the physical body which is made up of only lower level intelligence particles. Nevertheless, the collective lower level intelligence of the body has a strong influence on the soul and is constantly demanding to be satisfied with regard to over indulgence, luxurious living, entertainment, etc. which, for a very good reason, should be denied by the soul as explained above. After all, having endured such long periods of confinement in matter, man should strive for spiritual growth and freedom and not walk backwards in life.

[33] Just as the body has a surrounding energy field referred to as *aura*, so does the soul has an outer living-sphere. While the aura is closely knitted to the body the outer living-sphere of the soul can have a reach of several hundred or even thousands of kilometres. The soul uses the outer living-sphere to interact with its spiritual environment. In a crowded airport a person suddenly turns around and notices someone staring at him/her. Feeling the pain or joy of others is also accomplished through the outer living-sphere. Telepathy is another example of a soul becoming aware of the thoughts of another person several hundred kilometres away. Natural disasters are the work of millions of nature spirits collaborating to produce a certain physical outcome like a storm, earthquake or similar. A soul sensitive person can feel and see this energetic preparatory work of the nature spirits and is able to make clairvoyant predictions about coming events. Hypnosis and distance healing are also carried out through the means of the outer living sphere.

[34] Having said all the above about the soul, it should be borne in mind that the intelligence of the soul on its own is still limited to that of an intelligent animal. The soul receives its ability of higher reasoning from the divine spirit which is located in the heart of the soul. The divine spirit in man differentiates humans from animals. Adam and Eve were the first human couple on earth created by God about 6,000 years ago, endowed with a divine spirit, propelling an explosion of cultural and technological development to take place. The divine spirit, as a soft voice deep inside of us, provides the soul with the ability to distinguish between true and false and good and evil. The divine spirit an omnipotent, omniscient, intelligent divine force in man, does not have a form but provides the reason for the life, form and intelligence of the soul and body. Unlike the soul which is made up of countless individual intelligence particles, the divine spirit cannot be subdivided and exists as a whole. The divine spirit in man can be compared to a mirror pointed towards the sun. The sunlight reflected by the mirror has all the properties of sunlight with regard to content, heat and intensity but it is not the sun itself. In the same way all human beings are equipped with a perfect divine spark from God which is why it is written that we have been created in the image of God. By means of this divine spark we carry the love, wisdom and power of God in us. Through the divine spirit we are connected to God and to the whole of creation. It is the divine spirit which provides the soul with unlimited intelligence.

[35] Immediately the question arises: "How is it possible for man to be capable of the most evil deeds if he carries the perfect divine spirit of God in him?" The answer to this all important question is that the soul has an independent free will and can do what it wants. When a child is born the perfect divine spirit spark is placed inside the heart of the soul in a very secure minute shell. Only a very limited amount of the spirit's omnipotent intelligence and power is allowed to penetrate the soul and it also provides the soul with free willingness. In very rare cases the divine spirit is allowed to express itself in a slightly higher degree, giving rise to the phenomena of extremely gifted children like Mozart starting to compose music at the age of five. This initial intelligence and free willingness of the soul is sufficient for the soul to search, recognize and begin to love its Creator and by doing so can awaken the residing divine spirit. The soul can achieve this by not giving in to the powerful selfish call of its body and the world at large but in all humility search, recognize and love its Creator and its fellow-man. The soul is given a lifetime to learn and succeed in doing so allowing the divine spirit inside of the soul to become more and more awakened to such an extent that finally the soul and its spirit will merge to become one. This is then the real meaning of the rebirth of the soul in its divine spirit as it was explained by Jesus to Nicodemus in John 2:23. It is also the point in life where a person can say together with Paul "... I no longer live, but Christ lives in me." (Galatians 2:20). If the rebirth cannot be achieved here on earth, it can be accomplished in the beyond but under more difficult circumstances and it will take much longer. God, who incarnated Himself as the Son of Man, Jesus, was the first person to have achieved this at a very young age and taught mankind the real kingdom of God.

[36] Quite often the question is put forward: "But if I have to submit my will to God's will, then I do not have a free will any more?" When contemplating this on a deeper level it becomes clear that only in the perfect will of God can exist the highest degree of spiritual freedom and also the highest degree of bliss and joy. The free will of any created, developing being during its process of growth, must therefore necessarily be in some way impaired in its freedom. But the created beings of God are destined to become free as God is free and this can only happen if we submit our free will to God's will. This is why man has been created in such a way

to gradually lose his spiritual freedom the more he moves away from God's order. Which gave rise to the creation of the cosmic man (see separate article on the creation of the universe). Initially Lucifer was the most powerful arch angel created and enjoyed an incredible degree of spiritual freedom. But in his limitless freedom and power, Lucifer began to move away from God's order and in his supercilious delusion imagined being more powerful than His Creator. This led to his imprisonment in matter - which by the way he engineered himself knowingly because he was over many trillion of years educated that this will happen if he continues on his path of self-willingness - or the creation of the cosmic man who does not even have the power and freedom any more to lift his little finger.

[37] The initial intelligence and free will is given to the soul to search for its Creator through the means of inner and outer education and revelations. Inner revelations occur in many forms like clear dreams, visions, spiritual encounters and inner guidance through its conscience while outer revelations are given to the soul through family (initially mainly parents), friends, books, teachers, etc. but also through physical circumstances like unusual occurrences, illnesses, accidents or natural disasters. The soul needs to be alert to recognize all these occurrences as warning signs to mend its ways. For example man can keep destroying the rain forests for selfish reasons and thereby releasing trillions of nature-spirits prematurely into the atmosphere, which otherwise would have been occupied with plant growth in the forests. These suddenly unoccupied raw nature spirits can assemble in great masses in the atmosphere to produce the most violent, catastrophic storms. The soul now has the choice to either take remedial action or to ignore these warning signs resulting in more severe consequences. The same pattern can be observed on a much smaller scale in humans with regard to an increasing severity of illnesses. For a smoker it might start with an occasional coughing and end with lung cancer. In fact all natural disasters, famine, wars, accidents, illnesses, sufferings, etc. are self-inflicted reminders for the soul to return to the very inner destiny it was meant to be, namely to search for and love its Creator.

[38] The divine spirit inside the heart of the soul is an immense powerful entity and needs to be securely contained. Just imagine what would happen if the earth all of a sudden is placed next to the sun or if all the water of the oceans is poured into a teacup. Both the earth and the teacup would just disintegrate and cease to exist. The same would happen to the soul if the divine spirit is not securely encapsulated. The soul first needs to strengthen its willpower to be able to withstand the most powerful divine spirit of God inside of us. Only a minute amount of power and wisdom is allowed to escape the secure encapsulation and penetrate the soul to enable it to think on a higher level as it is graphically presented in Figure 8. The dark grey area surrounding the contained spiritual core, is where most of our thinking takes place. This kind of thinking in the dark is only an incoherent segregated thinking without understanding the whole, being the very reason why most of the things we undertake, always lead to dire consequences. The contemplation of war, revenge, hate, envy and other evilness is bred in the black fringes of the soul, furthest away from the divine centre. It is, however, possible, to learn to think more with the heart than the mind or to allow more and more of the wisdom of the heart (divine spirit) to guide the thinking of the mind.

Fig. 8: Graphical representation of the encapsulated divine spirit in the heart of the soul allowing only a minute amount of wisdom and power to penetrate the soul.

[39] Having covered the formation of matter from intelligence and describing the evolution of intelligence through the mineral-, plant- and animal kingdom up to the human soul, also addressing the spiritual anatomy of man, it is now time to look more closely at the Creator Himself. In the Bible the trinity of God is often referred to as the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit where the Father corresponds to the love in God, the Son refers to wisdom and the Holy Spirit means the power or will of God. Hence, the very nature of God is love, wisdom and will or power with love the most inner essence of God. The analogy for this trinity can be found in light where the warmth of light corresponds to love, the expanding light of light represents wisdom and the combined effect of warmth and light coincides with the will or power of God. Everything that exists regardless if physical or spiritual, has been created through this trinity. The smallest intelligence particles of being as described above can be regarded as the thoughts and ideas of God. These thoughts and ideas of God have form, intelligence, self consciousness, order and free-willingness. The free-willingness allows these thoughts and ideas to act according or against the implanted order. If a being acts against God's order it would eventually destroy itself. To prevent this from happening it is captured and imprisoned in matter to temporarily deprive it of its free-willingness and it has to endure the physical laws of matter.

[40] Nothing that has ever created by God can ever be destroyed again. If even one single tiniest intelligence particle would be able to cease to exist, it would mean that God is imperfect and God would allow to annihilate Himself which of course cannot happen. Everything that is created is destined to become free as God is free. Even the fallen Lucifer being imprisoned in matter (cosmic man), is destined to eventually return to the Father's house which is the true meaning of the prodigal son. It is entirely up to him how long he wants to endure the suffering of confinement (physical laws of matter) outside of the Father's house (unlimited freedom). It is the destiny of each human being, to freely recognize his Creator inside of himself and being gracefully privileged to work with God to bring back the fallen creatures. And when looking at the size of our physical universe and contemplating the infinite number of other universes making up the cosmic man, in crushing humbleness we realize that there is still a lot of work to be done to keep us pretty busy for the next couple of eternities.

[41] It has already been said that the most inner essence of God is the purest love. Love is thus the fundamental reason of the creation. Therefore God can only be found and honoured through a most sincere inner love but not through any outer form of worshipping. This love foundation resonates in everything we do, and applies to material love as well as spiritual love. Love is also the most powerful force inside of us. It is love which motivates a person to run into a burning house, in complete disregard for his own life, to save his loved ones. When reaching the age of twenty, loves drives us to look for a partner to establish a family and procreate children with whom we can share our love. We also find great joy when realizing that our children love us without forcing them to do so. It makes us even more happy if the children have grown up and have adapted our values with which we have raised them. This notion of love is in our genes because God created us for the very same reason. Unselfish, sacrificing love, the most incredible notion of human behaviour, could never have originated from 'dead' particles but only from the highest intelligence in eternity, namely God Himself. But love should not end with family love. In fact, family love has been given to us as a free gift to learn what love is. Once we gained the knowledge and experience of family love, it depends on us how to apply love for the rest of our lives. We can use the power of love to gather more and more riches for ourselves or to care for others. Figure 9 is the most simplest model of the meaning of life which can be understood by everyone. It stands above all religious, cultural, legal and political differences of all people who ever lived as well as all future generations to come and one doesn't even have to know how to read and write to understand it. Having received the schooling of family love for free, we are supposed to search for the love of God inside of ourselves and to care for others like we expect others to care for us.

